

Synthesis of 8-Substituted-10,11-Dihydro-11-Oxo-5H-Dibenzo [b, e]-1,4-Diazepines

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Manuscript received 18 September 1977, revised 6 March 1978, accepted 13 April 1978

8-Amino-10,11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo[b, e]-1,4-diazepine (2) synthesised by the cyclisation of 2', 4'-diaminodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (1), was converted to its chloro- and iodo derivatives (3 and 4) by Sandmeyer reaction, and to bromo derivative (5) by Gattermann reaction.

DIBENZODIAZEPINES are used as antihistaminic, antiparkinson and neuroleptic drugs^{1,2}. Tarpan³, noveril⁴ and clozapine⁵ are some marketed drugs of this class. Dibenzodiazepines having substituent (as chlorine) at position-7 showed good pharmacological activity⁶. In order to find out pharmacological activity or otherwise of dibenzodiazepines with substituents at position other than position-7, we synthesised analogous compounds having halogen substituents at position-8 starting from the corresponding 8-amino-10,11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo [b,e]-1,4-diazepine (2)⁷.

2,4-Dinitrochlorobenzene was reacted with anthranilic acid (Ullmann reaction) to give 2',4'-dinitro-diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (Ia)^{6,7} which was reduced with sodium dithionite to give 2',4'-diaminodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid (c.a. 61%), and the latter was cyclised to 8-amino-10,11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo [b,e]-1,4-diazepine (2). The amino group of the diazepine (2) was replaced by chlorine⁸, iodine⁹ and bromine¹⁰ to afford the halogenodiazepines (3-5).

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were recorded in DMSO on a varian-A-60D model using TMS as internal reference. The purity of the compounds was ascertained by tlc using silica gel-G as stationary phase and C₆H₆ : C₂H₅OH : NH₃ (7 : 2 : 1, solvent layer) as mobile phase.

8-Chloro-10,11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo [b,e]-1,4-diazepine (3)

The diazotised solution of the compound (2) (1.1250 g, 0.005M in 3 ml of conc. HCl, 2 ml

CH₃COOH and 0.4 g of NaNO₂ at 0-5°) was added to a cold solution of Cu₂Cl₂ (0.350 g dissolved in 1.50 ml of conc. HCl and 3 ml of water) at 0° with continuous stirring. After stirring at 20° for half an hour the reaction mixture was finally heated for 1 hr. over water bath when evolution of N₂ ceased. The contents were cooled and filtered. The crude product was crystallised from C₂H₅OH to afford the diazepine (3) (0.782 g, 63.99%), m.p 165°, Rf 0.65, (Found C, 64.02; H, 3.52; N, 11.56; Cl, 14.30, Calc. for C₁₃H₉ON₂Cl, C, 63.82; H, 3.68; N, 11.45; Cl, 14.54%) δ(DMSO): 6.15-6.50 (1H, bs, Ar-NH-Ar), 7.05-8.15 (7H, m, ArH) and 9.60 (1H, s, Ar-NH-Co-).

8-Iodo-10,11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo [b,e]-1,4-diazepine (4)

To a diazotised solution of the compound (2) (1.1250 g, 0.005M, in 3 ml of conc. HCl, 2 ml of CH₃COOH and 0.4 g NaNO₂ at 0-5°) ice cold solution of KI (1.0 g, 0.006M) was added in 15 min with stirring. The reaction mixture was warmed over water bath for one hour and the contents were exhaustively extracted with CHCl₃ after basification with aq. NaOH (10%). The CHCl₃ extract was washed with thiosulphate solution and solvent distilled off. The crude product was crystallised from C₂H₅OH to afford diazepine (4) (0.815 g, 42.51%, mp 140°, Rf 0.56; Found C, 46.64; H, 2.76; N, 8.48; I, 38.42; Calc. for C₁₃H₉ON₂I, C, 46.43; H, 2.68; N, 8.34; I, 37.80%) δ(DMSO) 6.15-6.50 (1H, bs, Ar-NH-Ar), 7.05-8.15 (7H, m, ArH) and 9.60 (1H, s, Ar-NH-Co-).

8-Bromo-10,11-dihydro-11-oxo-5H-dibenzo [b,e]-1,4-diazepine (5)

To the diazotised solution of compound (2) (1.1250 g, 0.005M in 3 ml of 40% HBr and 0.4 g NaNO₂ at 0-5°) copper powder (0.020 g) was added, and the contents were heated cautiously over water bath for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture after cooling was filtered. The crude product was crystallised from C₂H₅OH to afford the diazepine

(5) (0.896 g, ca 62%), m.p. 148°, Rf 0.60 (Found, C, 54.16; H, 3.26; N, 10.08; Br, 28.02. Calc. for $C_{13}H_9ON_2Br$ C, 53.98; H, 3.11; N, 9.69; Br, 27.68%). δ (DMSO) 6.15-6.50 (1H, bs, Ar-NH-Ar), 7.05-8.15 (7H, m, ArH) and 9.60 (1H, s, Ar-NH-Co-).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for providing necessary facilities, and one of the authors (R.G.) thanks CSIR for financial assistance.

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